

**МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА**

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**RELATIONSHIP OF OTHER TYPES OF DISEASES WITH EYE
DISEASES**

**Yuldashev Bakhrom Sabirjanovich¹, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich²,
Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna³, Rajapov Sarvar Safarboevich⁴
Department of Pathomorphology, Urganch Branch, Tashkent Medical
Academy, associate professor¹.**

**Tashkent Medical Academy, Urganch branch, "Pathomorphology"
department, Ph.D².**

**Tashkent Medical Academy, Urganch branch, "Obstetrics and
gynecology" department, Ph.D³.**

**Assistant of the "Clinical anatomy and histology" department of
Urganch branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy⁴.**

Relevance of the topic: today, the occurrence of eye diseases as a result of their organic connection with other diseases is one of the urgent problems of medicine. According to the World Health Organization, there are 65 million blind patients on earth, and some diseases can be manifested by changes in the eye and deterioration of vision, so various measures are being developed and promoted to the public to visit an ophthalmologist once a year.

For example, to detect cancer-head cancer at an early stage, it is necessary to regularly examine the eyes and not be indifferent to changes. Bleeding of the retina can indicate leukemia, and changes in the pigmented membrane can indicate melanoma, which can damage not only the skin, but also the eye. It is for this reason that it is recommended to be examined by an ophthalmologist at least once a year.

Diabetic eye bleeding is one of the earliest symptoms of type 2 diabetes. In most cases, this symptom is observed before constant thirst, weakness and fatigue. If these symptoms are paid attention to in time, the development of the disease can be prevented by changing the lifestyle and diet.

Hypertension and heart disease - In studies conducted by specialists in the United States and Europe, it was found that there is a connection between the narrowing of small blood vessels in the eyes and heart disease. In addition, these symptoms may indicate the development of hypertension.

Multiple Sclerosis-Inflammation of the optic nerves is observed in 75 percent of patients suffering from multiple sclerosis. But it is necessary to consult a neurologist, not to diagnose arbitrarily.

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Rheumatoid arthritis-dry eye syndrome is the most common ophthalmological symptom of rheumatoid arthritis. It is known that every fourth patient suffering from rheumatoid arthritis has vision problems. The point is that sooner or later the inflammatory chemicals in the arthritis patient's body will eventually damage the eyeball.

Purpose of work: as the purpose of the work, the origin of the disease, its prevalence, and distribution by gender were studied among citizens living in the city of Urganch.

Inspection method and materials: as a method and material of examination, the appeals of people living in Urganch city to private clinics and their anamnesis, laboratory-diagnostics and instrumental instruments were conducted.

Results obtained: in connection with the conducted scientific work, the citizens who complained about eye diseases were examined by gender and the following result was determined, that is, the majority of the citizens who applied were women, which in turn was observed more in women than in men. Table 1.

Distribution by gender. Table 1.

When studying the closeness of eye diseases with other diseases, as a complication safe head cancer is 10% of people, diabetes is 25% of people, hypertension disease is 40% of people, sclerosis is 15% of people as a result, people with rheumatoid arthritis disease is 10 people 10% organized. Table 2.

Complications of eye disease. Table 2.

The results of the conducted examination showed that eye diseases are related to other diseases, mainly in the asoart site, and it was observed that it was more common in women with hypertension, that is, 40% of the diseases in 70 women were related to complications of hypertension.

When studying the age of the disease, it was found that it occurs mainly in women over 60 years old. The occurrence of the disease at such an age was attributed to the fact that they did not go to the 6-monthly check-up for the prevention of ophthalmological diseases, and did not take the medicines recommended by the medical staff on time.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that any eye the origin of the disease is related to the complication of other diseases. As a result, people with eye diseases are forbidden to visit the family polyclinic at their place of residence once every six months in order to prevent other diseases. Because the underlying disease may be a complication of another disease.

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